

Studies in Xanthenes. Part I : Synthesis of Some Iodo and Cyanoxanthenes and Bixanthonyls

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Iodination of 2-hydroxy-, 3-hydroxy-, 3, 6-dihydroxy- and 3-hydroxy-6-methoxy-xanthone with iodine and iodic acid and ammonia and iodine has been studied and the structures of the iodo compounds obtained have been established by synthesis and/or NMR spectral data. The methyl ethers of the iodo derivatives have been converted into the cyano derivatives through Rosenmund-von Braun reaction. Some mono iodoxanthenes have been converted into bixanthonyls through Ullmann reaction.

THOUGH a few iodoxanthenes such as 2-iodoxanthone^{1,2}, 3-iodoxanthone³, 2-iodo-7-nitroxanthone⁴ and 2, 7-diiodoxanthone⁴ have been synthesised by indirect methods, direct iodination of xanthenes has not been studied so far.

The present work deals with the iodination of 2-hydroxy-, 3-hydroxy-, 3,6-dihydroxy-, and 3-hydroxy-6-methoxyxanthone with iodine and iodic acid and with ammonia and iodine.

Iodination of 2-hydroxyxanthone with iodine and iodic acid or with ammonia and iodine in one, two or three molar proportions gave only a mono iodoxanthone which has been assigned 2-hydroxy-1-iodoxanthone structure(Ia) as the NMR spectrum in DMSO showed only one doublet in the low field region at δ 8.2, which can be assigned to H-8. 2-Hydroxy-3-iodoxanthone would have given an additional one proton singlet due to H-1 in the same low field region. The structure has been confirmed by converting 2-methoxy-1-formyl xanthone, prepared according to Davies *et al*⁵, into 2-methoxy-1-cyano-xanthone(Ib) through its oxime. This was found to be identical on direct comparison with the cyanoxanthone obtained from the monoiodoxanthone by methylation and Rosenmund-von Braun reaction. Hydrolysis of the cyanoxanthone in alkaline conditions gave the cyano xanthone back. Hydrolysis with water, sulphuric acid and acetic acid mixture in equal proportion by volume for 16 hr. led to the elimination of the cyano group and also to demethylation.

I
Ia, R₁ = H ; R₂ = I
Ib, R₁ = CH₃ ; R₂ = CN

II
IIa, R₁ = R₃ = H ; R₂ = I
IIb, R₁ = CH₃ ; R₂ = I ; R₃ = H
IIc, R₁ = H ; R₂ = NO₂ ; R₃ = H
IId, R₁ = CH₃ ; R₂ = NO₂ ; R₃ = H
IIE, R₁ = CH₃ ; R₂ = CN ; R₃ = H
IIf, R₁ = R₃ = H ; R₂ = COOH
IIg, R₁ = R₃ = H ; R₂ = CHO
IIh, R₁ = H ; R₂ = R₃ = I
IIi, R₁ = CH₃ ; R₂ = R₃ = CN

3-Hydroxyxanthone on iodination with ammonia and iodine with one mole or excess of iodine and with one mole of iodine and iodic acid in alcohol gave a monoiodoxanthone. This has been assigned 3-hydroxy-4-iodoxanthone structure(IIa) on the basis of the NMR data, which showed two one-proton doublets ($J=9\text{Hz}$) in the low-field region at δ 8.00 and δ 8.08 indicating that the iodine atom is in the 4-position and not in the 2-position. With the iodine in the 2-position, the compound would have given a singlet and a doublet, due to the peri-protons. An up-field doublet at about δ 6.96 due to H-2 is also discernible. In the case of 3-hydroxy-2-iodoxanthone it would have been due to H-4, but then it should have been a singlet. The structure was confirmed by the synthesis of 3-methoxy-4-iodoxanthone(IIb) through an unambiguous route. 2-Nitroresorcinol and salicylic acid in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride and zinc chloride gave 2,2', 4-trihydroxy-3-nitrobenzophenone, which was cyclised to get 3-hydroxy-4-nitroxanthone(IIc). The methyl ether of this xanthone was reduced by sodium dithionite in alcohol to get 3-methoxy-4-aminoxanthone(IIId). This was diazotised and treated with potassium iodide, whereupon it gave the same methoxyiodoxanthone as obtained by methylation of the monoiodoxanthone obtained on iodination.

3-Methoxy-4-iodoxanthone on treatment with cuprous cyanide in dimethyl formamide gave 3-methoxy-4-cyanoxanthone(IIe), which could not be converted into the xanthone carboxylic acid by either acid or alkali hydrolysis carried out according to the method of Berger and Oliver⁶ by using 100% polyphosphoric acid resulted in a mixture of 3-methoxy and 3-hydroxyxanthone. 3-Hydroxyxanthone-4-carboxylic acid(IIf), however, was prepared by oxidising 3-hydroxy-4-formylxanthone⁷(IIg) with silver oxide and sodium hydroxide. The methoxycyanoxanthone on treatment with anhydrous aluminium chloride in benzene gave 3-hydroxy-4-cyanoxanthone.

3-Hydroxyxanthone on treatment with three moles and excess of iodine and iodic acid in alcohol gave a diiodo derivative. Its NMR spectrum in DMSO showed a doublet at δ 8.10 due to the peri-proton H-8 and singlet at δ 8.40 due to H-1, confirming the 3-hydroxy-2, 4-diiodoxanthone (IIh) structure. The methyl ether of this xanthone on treatment with cuprous cyanide in dimethyl formamide gave 3-methoxy-2, 4-dicyanoxanthone (IIIi).

3, 6-Dihydroxyxanthone gave a monoiodoxanthone with one mole of iodine and iodic acid in alcohol. The NMR spectrum of the monoiodoxanthone showed a two-proton doublet ($J=9\text{Hz}$) centred at δ 7.81, which could be assigned to the two peri-protons H-1 and H-8 in 3, 6-dihydroxy-4-iodoxanthane(IIIa). With Rosenmund-von Braun reaction the dimethylether of the 4-iodo derivative gave 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-cyanoxanthone (IIb).

III

- IIIa, $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{I}$
 IIIb, $R_1 = R_4 = R_6 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = R_5 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_3 = \text{CN}$
 IIIc, $R_1 = R_2 = R_6 = R_4 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = R_5 = \text{I}$
 IIId, $R_1 = R_6 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = R_5 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_3 = R_4 = \text{CN}$
 IIIe, $R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{I}$; $R_2 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$
 IIIf, $R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = R_6 = \text{I}$; $R_2 = R_5 = \text{H}$
 IIIg, $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_6 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{I}$; $R_5 = \text{CH}_3$
 IIIh, $R_1 = R_3 = \text{I}$; $R_2 = R_4 = R_6 = \text{H}$; $R_5 = \text{CH}_3$
 IIIi, $R_1 = R_3 = \text{CN}$; $R_2 = R_5 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_4 = R_6 = \text{H}$

3, 6-Dihydroxyxanthone gave a diiodo derivative with two moles of iodine and iodic acid and with one or two moles of iodine and ammonia. Its NMR spectrum showed two two-proton doublets only. The two-proton doublet ($J=9\text{Hz}$) at δ 7.95 was assigned to peri-protons H-1 and H-8, while another two-proton doublet ($J=9\text{Hz}$) at δ 7.00 to H-2 and H-7, up-field due to the hydroxyl groups in the ortho positions. The data confirms the symmetrical 3, 6-dihydroxy-4, 5-diiodoxanthone(IIIc) structure. This xanthone on methylation and Rosenmund-von Braun reaction gave 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-dicyanoxanthone (IIIId). Attempts to hydrolyse the cyanoxanthone failed to give the xanthone dicarboxylic acid.

3, 6-Dihydroxyxanthone gave a triiodo derivative on reaction with a little over 3 moles of iodine and iodic acid in alcohol. As the diiodoxanthone has the 4, 5-diiodo structure this product has been assigned 3, 6-dihydroxy-2, 4, 5-triiodoxanthone structure (IIIe). With ammonia and iodine either the above di- or a tetraiodoxanthone was obtained. When 3, 6-dimethoxy-2, 4, 5-triiodoxanthone was subjected to Rosenmund-von Braun reaction it gave 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-dicyanoxanthone, the iodine atom at 2-position being eliminated during reaction.

Iodination of 3, 6-dihydroxyxanthone with four moles of iodinating agents resulted in the formation of a tetraiodoxanthone, 3, 6-Dihydroxy-2, 4, 5, 7-tetraiodoxanthone structure (IIIIf) has been assigned to it. The dimethyl ether of this tetraiodoxanthone on treatment with cuprous cyanide gave 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-dicyanoxanthone(IIIId).

3-Hydroxy-6-methoxyxanthone was prepared by partial methylation of 3, 6-dihydroxyxanthone using one mole of dimethyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide. The same xanthone was synthesised through the condensation of 4-methoxy-2-hydroxybenzoic acid with resorcinol in the presence of zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride to get 2, 2', 4'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone(IVa) and cyclisation of this ketone under pressure in an autoclave. Methylation of the intermediate benzophenone gave the tetramethoxy benzophenone(IVb), same as that obtained by Grover *et al*⁸ by methylation of 2, 2', 4, 4'-tetrahydroxybenzophenone.

Iodination of 3-hydroxy-6-methoxyxanthone with one mole of iodine and iodic acid or one mole of excess of iodine and ammonia gave the 4-iodo derivative(IIIg). On methylation it gave 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone.

Iodination of this xanthone with three moles and excess of iodine and iodic acid in alcohol gave a diiodo derivative. Methylation of this gave a dimethoxydiiodoxanthone which was different from the 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-diiodoxanthone, described earlier. Again, iodination of 3, 6-dimethoxyxanthone carried out under similar conditions did not give any iodo derivative, which also suggests that the diiodo derivative must have 3-hydroxy-2, 4-diiodo-6-methoxyxanthone(IIIh) structure. The NMR spectrum in DMSO clearly shows a one-proton singlet at δ 8.36 which can be assigned to H-1 and a one-proton doublet ($J=9\text{Hz}$) at δ 8.10 which can be assigned to H-8. On methylation and Rosenmund-von Braun reaction it gave 3, 6-dimethoxy-2, 4-dicyanoxanthone(IIIi).

IV

- IVa, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$; $R_4 = \text{CH}_3$
 IVb, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{CH}_3$

The monoiodoxanthenes prepared in the course of this work were subjected to Ullmann reaction and bixanthonyls obtained. These have not been known to occur in nature so far and none has been prepared synthetically, though bixanthylyls such as secalonic acids⁹, ergochromes¹⁰, ergoflavin¹¹ and ergochrysin^{9,11} have been reported in the literature.

When 2-methoxy-1-iodoxanthone was subjected to Ullmann reaction it gave 2, 2'-dimethoxy-1, 1'-bixanthonyl (Va) which on demethylation gave 2, 2'-dihydroxy-1, 1'-bixanthonyl (Vb). 3-Methoxy-4-iodoxanthone on heating with activated copper-bronze at 250° gave 3, 3'-dimethoxy-4, 4'-bixanthonyl (VIa), demethylation of which resulted in 3, 3'-dihydroxy-4, 4'-bixanthonyl (VIb). Ullmann reaction on 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone resulted in a mixture of 3, 3', 6, 6'-tetramethoxy-4, 4'-bixanthonyl (VIc), 3, 6-dimethoxyxanthone and 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone from which the bixanthonyl was isolated by TLC. Because of poor yield demethylation could not be carried out.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra are recorded on Beckman IR-20 model and NMR spectra on Perkin-Elmer model (90 MHz). Methylation is done in dry acetone in presence of potassium carbonate and acetylation by heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride.

2-Hydroxy-1-iodoxanthone : 2-Hydroxyxanthone (1.06 g.) was dissolved in warm ethyl alcohol (20 ml) and iodine (0.51 g.) in ethyl alcohol (18 ml.) added to it with stirring followed by iodic acid (0.18 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of water. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 hr and the separated product together with the product obtained after dilution of the reaction mixture with water crystallised from acetic acid as brownish needles (1.0 g.), m.p. 208-10°, IR (nujol) V_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 1630 (>CO). (Found : C, 45.88 ; H, 2.34 ; I, 37.57. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_7\text{O}_5\text{I}$ requires C, 46.15 ; H, 2.07 ; I, 37.57%).

Va, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OCH}_3$
Vb, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OH}$

The same monoiodo derivative was obtained when 2-hydroxyxanthone (0.53 g.) in aqueous ammonia (20% ; 150 ml.) was treated with iodine (0.64 g.) in potassium iodide (1.4 g.) dropwise with stirring

during half an hour. The solution was acidified with cold dilute sulphuric acid and treated with a pinch of sodium sulphite to remove free iodine. The separated product crystallised from acetic acid.

The methyl ether : m. p. 183-84°. (Found : C, 47.55 ; H, 2.24 ; I, 35.60. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{I}$ requires C, 47.73 ; H, 2.05 ; I, 36.07%).

2-Methoxy-1-cyanoxanthone : 2-Methoxy-1-iodoxanthone (0.7 g.) in dimethyl formamide (8 ml.) was refluxed with cuprous cyanide (0.2 g.) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and diluted with water when a yellow product separated, which was stirred with ammonia solution in portions till it did not give blue colour and then crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 266-68°. Yield 0.45 g. IR (nujol) v_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2220 (CN) ; 1650 (>CO). (Found : C, 71.39 ; H, 3.48 ; N, 5.38. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires C, 71.71 ; H, 3.61 ; N, 5.57%). The same compound was obtained as follows for comparison.

2-Methoxy-1-formylxanthone (0.5 g.), prepared according to Davies *et al.*⁸, was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.25 g.) in alcohol in the presence of potassium hydroxide (0.2 g.) for 2 hr. The yellow product obtained crystallised from aqueous alcohol. M. P. 226-28°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 67.87 ; H, 3.85 ; N, 5.01. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 68.25 ; H, 4.08 ; N, 5.22%).

The above oxime (0.4 g.) was refluxed in acetic anhydride (5.0 ml.) for 15 minutes and then poured into ice cold water and left overnight. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid. M. P. 266-68°. Yield 0.25 g. Mixed m.p. with the above cyanoxanthone was not depressed.

3-Hydroxy-4-iodoxanthone : 3-Hydroxyxanthone (1.06 g.) was dissolved in warm ethyl alcohol (25 ml.) and iodine (0.51 g.) in ethyl alcohol (18 ml.) added to it. The solution was stirred and iodic acid (0.2 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water was added gradually and the stirring continued for further 2 hr. The separated product and the product obtained after dilution with water crystallised from aqueous alcohol in yellowish needles. (1.2 g.), m.p. 246-47°. IR (nujol) V_{\max} , cm^{-1} ; 1640 (>CO). (Found : C, 46.34 ; H, 2.43 ; I, 37.22. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_7\text{O}_5\text{I}$ requires C, 46.15 ; H, 2.07 ; I, 37.57%).

The same monoiodoxanthone was obtained when powdered 3-hydroxyxanthone (0.5 g.) was dissolved in aqueous ammonia (20% ; 150 ml.) and treated with iodine (0.64 g.) in potassium iodide (1.4 g.) solution in water (30 ml.). The product obtained on acidification with cold dilute sulphuric acid was crystallised from aqueous alcohol. Yield 1.1 g.

The methyl ether : M.p. 189°. (Found : C, 47.55 ; H, 2.48 ; I, 35.92. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{I}$ requires C, 47.73 ; H, 2.06 ; I, 36.07%).

The acetyl derivative : M.p. 199°. (Found : C, 47.22 ; H, 2.66 ; I, 32.96. $C_{18}H_9O_4I$ requires C, 47.38 ; H, 2.37 ; I, 33.16%.)

VIa, $R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$; $R_3 = R_4 = H$
 VIb, $R_1 = R_2 = OH$; $R_3 = R_4 = H$
 VIc, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = OCH_3$

Synthesis of 3-methoxy-4-iodoxanthone : 2, 2', 4-Trihydroxy-3-nitrobenzophenone : A mixture of 2-nitroresorcinol (5.0 g.) and salicylic acid (4.0 g.) together with anhydrous zinc chloride (12.0 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (28 ml.) was kept in a water bath at 60-65° for 3 hr. On pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice a gummy mass separated which was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and then with water and taken in 10% sodium hydroxide solution. This was boiled for half an hour and acidified after cooling. The separated gummy mass was crystallised from water (1 litre) and then taken in chloroform and passed through silica gel column. The product obtained after removal of the solvent crystallised from aqueous methanol. M.p. 118-20°. Yield 0.8 g. The benzophenone was analysed after drying overnight at 100° under vacuum. (Found : C, 57.18 ; H, 3.09 ; N, 4.70. $C_{18}H_9O_6N$ requires C, 56.73 ; H, 3.27 ; N, 5.09%.)

3-Hydroxy-4-nitroxanthone : The above benzophenone (0.5 g) was dissolved in aqueous alcohol (30% ; 20 ml.) and the solution was heated in a sealed Carius tube at 220° for 3 hr. The cyclised product was again crystallised from aqueous alcohol as yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 218-20°. This showed brownish red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found after drying under vacuum at 110° : C, 60.75 ; H, 2.67 ; N, 5.17 ; $C_{18}H_7O_5N$ requires 60.70 ; H, 2.73 ; N, 5.45%.)

The Methyl ether : M.p. 250-52°. (Found C, 62.43 ; H, 3.77 ; N, 5.59. $C_{14}H_9O_5N$ requires C, 61.99 ; H, 3.32 ; N, 5.17%.)

3-Methoxy-4-aminoxanthone : 3-Methoxy-4-nitroxanthone (0.3 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (90 ml.) and sodium dithionite (0.5 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed and hot water (15 ml.) was added and heating continued for half an hour. Most of the alcohol was then removed under vacuum and the solution poured into ice-cold water. The separated product crystallised from aqueous alcohol in

light yellow needles (0.2 g.). m.p. 175-76°. (Found : C, 69.85 ; H, 4.73 ; N, 5.51. $C_{14}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 69.75 ; H, 4.56 ; N, 5.80%.)

3-Methoxy-4-iodoxanthone : 3-Methoxy-4-aminoxanthone (0.2 g.) was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid (30 % ; 18 ml.) by warming and the solution was then cooled to 0°. This mixture was stirred and sodium nitrite solution (0.3 g. in 3 ml. water) was added with constant stirring and the reaction mixture was left for half an hour at 0 - .5° and urea (0.5 g.) was added followed by potassium iodide (0.5 g.) in water (5 ml.). The solution was stirred well for an hour and was kept at 60° for one hour more. The excess of iodine was removed by adding sodium sulphite. The separated product crystallised from alcohol as white needles (0.22 g.). The mixed m.p. of this compound with the methyl ether of 3-hydroxy-4-iodoxanthone described above was not depressed.

3-Methoxy-4-cyanoxanthone : 3-Methoxy-4-iodoxanthone (0.7 g.) and cuprous cyanide (0.2 g.) were refluxed in dimethyl formamide (8 ml.) for 4 hr. The solution was filtered hot and diluted with water. The separated solid was treated further with ammonia and then crystallised from acetic acid in white needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 272-73°. IR (KBr) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 2230 (-CN) ; 1660 (>CO). (Found : C, 71.93 ; H, 3.45 ; N, 5.35. $C_{15}H_9O_5N$ requires C, 71.71 ; H, 3.61 ; N, 5.57 %.)

3-Hydroxyxanthone-4-carboxylic acid : Silver oxide prepared from silver nitrate (0.4 g.) and sodium hydroxide (0.1 g. in 8 ml water) was suspended in sodium hydroxide solution (0.5 g. in 10 ml. water). To this stirred solution, kept at 60°, paste prepared from 3-hydroxy-4-formylxanthone (0.48 g.) and sodium hydroxide solution (2N, 2 ml.) was added slowly. Stirring was continued for further 4 hr. and then the reaction mixture was left overnight. Next day it was filtered and the filtrate acidified. The solid obtained was purified by sodium bicarbonate extraction and crystallised from aqueous acetic acid in white needles (0.18 g.), m.p. 222°. The product showed pink colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. IR (nujol) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} ; 3450 (-OH) ; 1670 (-COOH) ; 1630 (>CO). (Found after drying at 110° under vacuum : C, 65.37 ; H, 2.83. $C_{14}H_5O_8$ requires C, 65.63 ; H, 3.15%.)

3-Hydroxy-4-cyanoxanthone : 3-Methoxy-4-cyanoxanthone (0.5 g.) in benzene (50 ml.) was refluxed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.0 g.) for 2 hr. On working up the reaction mixture, an alkali soluble product was obtained, which crystallised from aqueous acetic acid in white needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 310°. IR (nujol) ν_{max} , cm^{-1} : 3450 (-OH) ; 2222 (-CN) ; 1630 (>CO). (Found after drying at 110° under vacuum : C, 71.40 ; H, 3.06 ; N, 6.08. $C_{14}H_7O_5N$ requires C, 70.88 ; H, 2.91 ; N, 5.82%.)

3-Hydroxy-2, 4-diiodoxanthone : To 3-hydroxyxanthone (1.06 g.) in alcohol (30 ml.) iodine (1.53 g.)

was added followed by warm alcohol (40 ml.) with stirring. To this solution iodic acid (0.54 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water was added. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 2 hr. and the separated needles recrystallised from alcohol when tiny yellow needles (1.2 g.) m. p. 242-43°, were obtained. IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 1640 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$). (Found: C, 33.44; H, 1.40; I, 54.92. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{I}_2$ requires C, 33.62; H, 1.29; I, 54.74%).

The methyl ether: M. p. 175-76°. (Found: C, 35.53; H, 1.81; I, 52.76. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{I}_2$ requires C, 35.14; H, 1.67; I, 53.13%).

The acetyl derivative: M. p. 252-53°. (Found: C, 35.17; H, 1.53; I, 50.19. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{I}_2$ requires C, 35.75; H, 1.58; I, 50.19%).

3-Methoxy-2, 4-dicyanoxanthone: A mixture of 3-methoxy-2, 4-diiodoxanthone (0.7 g.) and cuprous cyanide (0.38 g.) was refluxed in dimethyl formamide (10 ml.) for 2 hr. The solution was filtered hot and then worked up as before. The product crystallised from acetic acid in white needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 280°. IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2222 ($-\text{CN}$); 1670 ($>\text{CO}$). (Found: C, 70.05; H, 3.28; N, 9.86. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires, C, 69.56; H, 2.92; N, 10.14%).

3, 6-Dihydroxy-4-iodoxanthone: 3, 6 Dihydroxyxanthone (1.14 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (75 ml.) by warming and iodine (0.51 g.) added to it, followed by more alcohol (15 ml). Iodic acid (0.18 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of water was then added with stirring. After about 2 hr. the solution was diluted and the separated product crystallised from alcohol in light pink needles (0.58 g.), m.p. 340° (decomp.). IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 1615 ($>\text{CO}$). (Found: C, 43.77; H, 1.85; I, 35.89. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_7\text{O}_4\text{I}$ requires C, 43.94; H, 1.97; I, 35.78%).

The dimethyl ether: M. p. 249-50°. (Found: C, 47.00; H, 2.55; I, 32.82. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{I}$ requires C, 47.12; H, 2.88; I, 33.24%).

The diacetyl derivative: M. p. 201-03°. (Found: C, 46.22; H, 2.21; I, 29.35. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{I}$ requires C, 46.57; H, 2.51; I, 28.93%).

3, 6-Dimethoxy-4-cyanoxanthone: A mixture of 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone (0.7 g.) and cuprous cyanide (0.3 g.) in dimethyl formamide (10 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. This was filtered hot and the filtrate diluted with water. The separated solid was washed with ammonia and crystallised from acetic acid. M.p. 293°. Yield 0.5 g. IR (hexachlorobutadiene) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2230 ($-\text{CN}$); 1660 ($>\text{CO}$). (Found: C, 66.76; H, 3.98; N, 4.98. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 66.91; H, 4.09; N, 5.20%).

3, 6-Dihydroxy-4-5-diiodoxanthone: 3, 6-Dihydroxyxanthone (1.14 g.) dissolved in alcohol (75 ml.) was iodinated with iodine (1.02 g.) in alcohol (30 ml.) and iodic acid (0.35 g.) and the reaction mixture

worked up as before. The diiodoxanthone crystallised from alcohol as light yellow needles (1.2 g.) m.p. 266-68° (decomp.). IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 1640 ($>\text{CO}$). (Found: C, 32.18; H, 1.44; I, 52.95. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{I}_2$ requires C, 32.50; H, 1.25; I, 52.94%).

The same product was obtained when 3, 6-dihydroxyxanthone (1.14 g.) was dissolved in ammonia (20%; 150 ml.) and iodine (1.27 g.) and potassium iodide (2.6 g.) in water was added slowly with constant stirring and then acidified. Yield 0.9 g. The same product was obtained in better yield with double the quantity of iodine.

The dimethyl ether: M.p. 301°. (Found: C, 35.78; H, 2.38; I, 50.27. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{I}_2$ requires C, 35.40; H, 1.97; I, 49.99%).

The acetyl derivative: M. p. 235-36°. (Found: C, 36.44; H, 1.17; I, 45.40. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{I}_2$ requires C, 36.16; H, 1.77; I, 45.03%).

3, 6-Dimethoxy-4, 5-dicyanoxanthone: A mixture of 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-diiodoxanthone (0.5 g.) and cuprous cyanide (0.4 g.) in dimethyl formamide (15 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow buds (0.17 g.), m.p. 373°. (Found: C, 66.19; H, 3.24; N, 9.33. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.27; N, 9.15%).

3, 6-Dihydroxy-2, 4, 5-triiodoxanthone: 3, 6-Dihydroxyxanthone (1.14 g.) in alcohol (75 ml.) was treated with iodine (1.5 g.) in alcohol (50 ml.) followed by iodic acid in minimum quantity of water and the reaction mixture stirred at 60° for 2 hr. The separated product crystallised from acetic acid in pinkish needles (1.9 g.), m.p. 264-65°. IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 1630 ($>\text{CO}$). (Found: C, 25.26; H, 1.00; I, 62.44. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{I}_3$ requires C, 25.58; H, 0.83; I, 62.87%).

The dimethyl ether: M. p. 268-69°. (Found: C, 28.21; H, 1.55; I, 59.89. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{I}_3$ requires C, 28.39; H, 1.42; I, 60.09%).

The diacetyl derivative: M. p. 235-36°. (Found: C, 29.50; H, 1.55; I, 54.91. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{I}_3$ requires C, 29.56; H, 1.30; I, 55.22%).

Rosenmund-von Braun reaction on 3, 6-dimethoxy-2, 4, 5-triiodoxanthone: 3, 6-Dimethoxy-2, 4, 5-triiodoxanthone (0.8 g.) was mixed with cuprous cyanide (0.4 g.) and refluxed in dimethyl formamide (20 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained after working up, crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow buds (0.15 g.), m.p. 371-73°. The mixed m.p. with 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-dicyanoxanthone was not depressed.

3, 6-Dihydroxy-2, 4, 5, 7-tetraiodoxanthone: To a mixture of 3, 6-dihydroxyxanthone (1.14 g.) and iodine (2.04 g.) in alcohol (150 ml.), iodic acid (0.71 g.) in water was added and the solution stirred at

70° for 2 hr. The separated product crystallised from excess of acetic acid in yellow needles (2.1 g.) m. p. 285-86°. IR (nujol) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 1650 (>CO). (Found : C, 21.04 ; H, 0.61 ; I, 68.98. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_4\text{O}_4\text{I}_4$ requires C, 21.31 ; H, 0.55 ; I, 69.40%).

The same product was obtained when 3, 6-dihydroxyxanthone (1.14 g.) in ammonia (20% ; 200 ml.) was treated with iodine (5.08 g.) and potassium iodide (10.0 g.) in water (30 ml.).

The dimethyl ether : M. p. 266-67°. (Found : C, 23.55 ; H, 1.33 ; I, 66.48. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{I}_4$ requires C, 23.69 ; H, 1.24 ; I, 66.85%).

The diacetyl derivative : M. p. 271°. (Found : C, 25.33 ; H, 1.36 ; I, 61.86. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_8\text{O}_6\text{I}_4$ requires C, 25.00 ; H, 0.99 ; I, 62.26%).

Rosenmund-von Braun reaction on 3, 6-dimethoxy-2, 4, 5, 7-tetraiodoxanthone : The reaction was carried out as in the case of the triiodo derivative and the product obtained was again 3, 6-dimethoxy-4, 5-dicyanoxanthone.

3-Hydroxy-6-methoxyxanthone : 3, 6-Dihydroxyxanthone (7.0 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution (2.5 g. in 20 ml. of water) was treated with dimethyl sulphate (3.5 ml.) with stirring and the solution was stirred further for an hour and then refluxed for 15 minutes. The separated 3, 6-dimethoxyxanthone was filtered off and the filtrate acidified. The separated product was crystallised from alcohol in needles (2.3 g.), m. p. 304-05°. (Found : C, 69.00 ; H, 3.85. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 69.42 ; H, 4.16%).

2, 2', 4-trihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone : A mixture of 4-methoxysalicylic acid (5.0 g.) and resorcinol (5.0 g.) was heated in the presence of zinc chloride (20.0 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (28 ml.) in a water bath at 60-65° for 3 hr. The reaction mixture on pouring in water gave a gummy mass which was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, then with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution. Repeated crystallisation from aqueous alcohol gave yellow needles (2.3 g.), m. p. 101-02°. This showed brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found after drying under vacuum at 70° : C, 64.15 ; H, 4.81. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 64.61 ; H, 4.65%). The tetramethyl ether gave m. p. 126-28° same as reported by Grover et al⁸. The triacetyl derivative gave m. p. 133°. (Found : C, 61.81 ; H, 4.34. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 62.17 ; H, 4.70%).

Cyclisation : The above benzophenone (1.0 g.) was dissolved in aqueous alcohol (30% ; 20 ml.) and heated in a sealed tube at 200-20° for 2 hr. The separated product crystallised from alcohol in needles (0.7 g.), m. p. 304-05°.

The monoacetyl derivative : M. p. 178°. (Found : C, 67.20 ; H, 3.79. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 67.60 ; H, 4.25%).

3-Hydroxy-4-iodo-6-methoxyxanthone : 3-Hydroxy-6-methoxyxanthone was iodinated with ammonia and iodine and iodic acid following the procedure described for 3, 6-dihydroxy-4-iodoxanthone. The product gave m. p. 255-58°. (Found : C, 45.39 ; H, 2.45 ; I, 34.97. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{I}$ requires C, 45.65 ; H, 2.45 ; I, 34.51%). The dimethyl ether, m. p. 249-50°, was found to be identical with 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone.

The acetyl derivative : M. p. 225°. (Found : C, 47.32 ; H, 2.74 ; I, 31.09. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{I}$ requires C, 46.82 ; H, 2.68 ; I, 30.97%).

3-Hydroxy-2, 4-diiodo-6-methoxyxanthone : 3-Hydroxy-6-methoxyxanthone (0.48 g.) in warm alcohol and iodine (1.5 g.) in alcohol (45 ml.) were stirred together and iodic acid (0.53 g.) in water was added. The product separating after 2 hr. crystallised from acetic acid. M. p. 248-51°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 34.22 ; H, 1.40 ; I, 51.84. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{I}_2$ requires C, 34.00 ; H, 1.61 ; I, 51.40%).

The methyl ether : M. p. 256° (Found : C, 35.90 ; H, 2.08 ; I, 49.86. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{I}_2$ requires C, 35.43 ; H, 1.96 ; I, 50.00%).

The acetyl derivative : M. p. 240-41°. (Found : C, 36.20 ; H, 1.89 ; I, 47.78. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5\text{I}_2$ requires C, 35.82 ; H, 1.86 ; I, 47.38%).

3, 6-Dimethoxy-2, 4-dicyanoxanthone : The Rosenmund-von Braun reaction was carried out on 3, 6-dimethoxy-2, 4-diiodoxanthone as described before and the product crystallised from acetic acid. M. p. 253°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 67.13 ; H, 3.75 ; N, 9.30. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 66.67 ; H, 3.27 ; N, 9.15%).

2, 2'-Dimethoxy-1, 1'-bixanthonyl : 2-Methoxy-1-iodoxanthone (1.0 g.) was mixed with activated copper bronze (1.0 g.) and heated in an oil bath between 250-60° for 20 minutes. The mass was extracted with hot dimethyl formamide (10 ml.) and filtered. The filtrate on cooling gave yellow which were recrystallised from acetic acid. M. p. 331-2°. Yield 0.18 g. (Found : C, 74.49 ; H, 3.82. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 74.66 ; H, 4.00%).

2, 2'-Dihydroxy-1, 1'-bixanthonyl : 2, 2'-Dimethoxy-1, 1'-bixanthonyl (0.5 g.) in benzene (50 ml.) when refluxed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.0 g.) for 3 hr. gave on working up as usual, an alkali soluble product which crystallised from acetic acid in shining yellow needles (0.3 g.), m. p. 342-43°. (Found : C, 73.89 ; H, 3.31. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 73.93 ; H, 3.34%).

3, 3'-Dimethoxy-4, 4'-bixanthonyl : Prepared from 3-methoxy-4-iodoxanthone as in the previous case and crystallised from acetic acid gave m. p. 284-85°. (Found : C, 74.24 ; H, 4.26. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 74.66 ; H, 4.00%).

3, 3'-Dihydroxy-4, 4'-bixanthonyl: The above bixanthonyl was demethylated as before and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow buds. M. p. 375-77°. (Found: C, 73.56; H, 3.56 C₂₆H₁₄O₆ requires C, 73.93; H, 3.34%).

3, 3', 6, 6'-Tetramethoxy-4, 4'-bixanthonyl: 3,6-Dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone (1.0 g) was heated with copper bronze (1.0 g.) at 260-80° for 20 minutes and the mass extracted with hot dimethyl formamide (10 ml.) The solid obtained on dilution with water was subjected to thin layer chromatography using silica gel, with chloroform as a solvent. The upper band which showed a dark blue fluorescence in UV light, was the deiodinated 3, 6-dimethoxyxanthone (m.p. 186°); the middle band which showed light blue fluorescence was the bixanthonyl (m.p. 305-06°) and the last band was of the original 3, 6-dimethoxy-4-iodoxanthone. The middle band was taken in chloroform and further purified by TLC and then taken up in chloroform. After removing the solvent the product crystallised from acetic acid in white needles (0.08 g), m.p. 305.06° (Found: C, 70.83; H, 4.43. C₃₀H₂₂O₈ requires C, 70.58; H, 4.34%).

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